

MICROHARDNESS AND COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED Ti/HA BIOMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Functionally graded materials *Titanium/Hydroxyapatite* (Ti/HA) at three weight percents of composition ($n=0.8, 1$ and 1.2) have been fabricated. Five layers were prepared in FGMs graded from 1st layer as pure Ti to 5th layer as HA with homogeneous gradient in composition for the other layers. Some mechanical properties were measured for fabricated FGMs include microhardness, compression, modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio.

The results showed that the microhardness increases from 1st layer to 5th layer. While for the same layer, microhardness decreases with increasing (n) value due to decreasing HA percent in layer. On other hand, compressive strength increases with increasing (n) value due to increasing Ti percent in same layer.

The modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio were calculated for fabricated FGMs, and the results showed the decreasing of elasticity and Poisson's ration from 1st layer (Ti) to 5th layer (HA) because of brittleness of ceramic hydroxyapatite.

This gradient in mechanical properties candidates the fabricated FGM to use it as biomaterial because of approaching to mechanical properties of bone in body.

Keywords: Hardness; Mechanical testing; Powder processing.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of materials are of great importance when designing load-bearing orthopedic and dental implants. The mismatch of mechanical properties between metallic and ceramic materials can cause "stress shielding," a condition characterized by bone resorption (loss of bone) in the vicinity of implants.

Compared with the elastic moduli of either stainless steel or cobalt-chromium molybdenum alloys, Ti and Ti-6Al-4V have much lower (approximately half) moduli that are still almost an order of magnitude higher than that of bone. Another advantage of Ti-based metals as a bone implant material is their favorable strength-to-density ratio.

The major drawbacks to the use of ceramics and glasses as implants are their brittleness and poor tensile properties. Although they can have outstanding strength when loaded in compression, ceramics and glasses fail at low stress when loaded in tension or bending. The mechanical properties of calcium phosphates and bioactive glasses make them unsuitable as load-bearing implants. Clinically, hydroxyapatite has been used as filler for bone defects and as an implant in load-free anatomic sites.

In addition, hydroxyapatite has been used as a coating on metallic orthopedic and dental implants to promote their fixation in bone. In these cases, the underlying metal carries the load, whereas the surrounding bone strongly bonds to hydroxyapatite.

Many researchers highlighted fabrication and characterization of metal/metal and metal/ceramic FGMs in addition to study their physical, chemical and mechanical properties [1-8].

The aim of present work is measure some mechanical properties of fabricated FGMs at $n= 0.8, 1$ and 1.2 according to mathematical calculations with five layers to estimate the possibility of using these materials as bioimplants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

FGM-samples were prepared using a powder metallurgical process by the layers pressing method. Metallic and ceramic powders were mixed in several proportions. After mixing process, the mixtures were stacked layer by layer with a concentration difference in components content like in Table (1). The powder of layers is measured by sensitive balance type (BEL), which estimated by the following formula:

$$w_L = \rho_L \times V_L \times V_1 \dots (1)$$

Where w_L and ρ_L are weight and density of powder layer, V_L is layer volume and V_1 is volume fraction.

Pure Ti with purity 98.5% and average particle size $165 \mu\text{m}$ obtained from Fluka chemi AGCH-9470 Buckes was used in fabrication. Hydroxyapatite with purity 99.8% and average particle size $42 \mu\text{m}$ obtained from India used as ceramic material in fabricated FGMs. Wet mixing was used by Ball Mills type PM200 with rotational speed of 300 rpm for 1 hr. Cold uniaxial pressing in double action dies has been practiced with 50 mm height, 12 mm interior diameter and 32 mm outer diameter.

Sintering process was achieved in quartz tube which placed in furnace type (Thermco-model mini brute 201) at 1000°C for 2 hr.

Microhardness Vickers tester type (Digital Display microhardness Tester model Hv-1000) was used in this work to measure hardness with 200g load and holding time of 20 seconds to the surface of the specimen using a standard 136°

Vickers diamond pyramid indenter combined with optical microscopy to measure the diagonal length of Vicker's impression. The Vicker's microhardness (HV) is specified as follows:

$$HV = 1.854 \frac{P}{d^2} \dots\dots(2)$$

where: P = Applied load (gm/mm²) and d = Average length of diagonal (mm).

The compression test was done according to ASTM (D95-85) at the room temperature at the crosshead speed of 1mm/min using the universal testing machine model (instron 5864).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Because of good mechanical of titanium and good biocompatibility of hydroxyapatite, they have been selected to fabricate biomaterial combined from metal/ceramic composite as functionally graded materials (FGMs). Ti/HA FGMs were fabricated at three values of (n) to get gradient in composition of their layers as listed in Table (1). (n) values were calculated according to Wakashima et al. [1].

The characterization of these materials was achieved in previous paper, which indicated the phases which formed between the two materials (Ti and HA). These phases were produced from partially decomposed of hydroxyapatite into CaO and Ca₄O(PO₄)₂ (TTCP), also some Ti converted to Ti₂O, in addition to form Ti₄P₃, while Ti₄P₃ is produce at the Ti/HA interfaces. This characterization was estimated by XRD and SEM with EDS analysis [9].

Thermal and mechanical processing conditions can change the microstructure of materials. FGMs spatially vary composite microstructure or composition to optimize resultant material properties. Compositional gradients take advantage of multiple material properties and avoid the stress-strain concentrations that occur at sharp interfaces of different materials. Dependent on the microstructure, material properties vary with position within the gradient and can be used to tailor composite performance and functionality.

The hardness of material must be sufficient to resist wear from opposing teeth or restorations and not so hard as to wear enamel (which has a Vicker's hardness of 340 kg/mm²) and other materials such as porcelain. In practice, a Vicker's hardness less than 125 kg/mm² makes a material susceptible to wear, and hardness greater than enamel may wear existing teeth [10, 11]. However, wear is a complex phenomenon, and predicting clinical wear based on hardness alone is not advisable [12]. Information on hardness is commonly available from manufacturers.

Figure (1) shows the Vicker's microhardness of fabricated FGMs at three n values as a function to HA percentage. This figure indicates that the microhardness increases from 1st layer (Ti) to 5th layer (HA)

It should be noted that the Vickers hardness decreased with increasing metal content. This is mainly attributed to the pores in intermediate layers in the FGM after sintering stage, where the pores were increased in the FGM layers with increasing metal content [13]. This result candidate the fabricated FGMs as biomaterials because of delamination of the ceramic layer from the metal surface, however, can create serious problems and lead to implant failure in non FGMs, while in this study the microhardness values were higher than 125 kg/mm².

Figure (2) shows the relationship between microhardness and thickness of layers in fabricated FGMs, this figure candidate the FGM at $n=0.8$.

The compressive strength of all dental alloys is sufficiently high that it is not a consideration for clinical performance; however, tensile strength varies considerably among alloys. Figure (3) shows the compressive strength of fabricated FGMs, from this figure can be seen that the compressive strength increases with increasing (n) value because of increasing the titanium content in layers and approaching to the compressive strength of human bone (170 MPa).

The elastic moduli and strength of titanium and its alloys are much higher than those of human bones, which may result in stress shielding and the failure of implants. People have tried to develop new types of titanium alloys, such as β -Ti alloys, to reduce the modulus of the implants to the level approaching human bones. On the other hand, the mechanical properties of porous titanium can be adjusted by pore fraction and morphology, and the stress shielding effect will be reduced.

Figure (4) shows the modulus of elasticity for fabricated FGMs, it can be noticed that the values of modulus of elasticity decrease from 1st layer (Ti) to 5th layer (HA) due to decreasing in Ti content. For the same layer, modulus of elasticity increases with increasing (n) value. This result illustrates the sufficient role for FGMs as biomaterial due to reducing the modulus of elasticity and approaching to the modulus of elasticity of human bone. The same result was obtained for Poisson's ratio as shown in Figure (5).

CONCLUSION

The new technology highlights to discover new materials as bioimplants which achieve the requirements of various functions in human body. Functionally graded materials have the wide range to use as biomaterials due to homogeneous in their layers to reduce some undesired properties. In this study, we tested three

fabricated Ti/HA FGMs as bioimplant through exam microhardness, compressive strength, modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio. The results showed the good mechanical properties of fabricated materials for approaching to mechanical properties of bone in human body through the phases which formed between titanium and hydroxyapatite especially after sintering at 1000°C to produce bioactive compounds with good properties.

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Table (1): Chemical composition of FGM layers at different (n) values.

No. of layer	Thickness (mm)	<i>n=0.8</i>	<i>n=1</i>	<i>n=1.2</i>
		Composition (%)	Composition (%)	Composition (%)
1 st layer	3	100Ti	100Ti	100Ti
2 nd layer	2.5	67.1Ti-32.9HA	75Ti-25HA	81.1Ti-18.9HA
3 rd layer	2	42.6Ti-57.4HA	50Ti-50HA	56.5Ti-43.5HA
4 th layer	1.5	20.6Ti-79.4HA	25Ti-75HA	29.2Ti-70.8HA
5 th layer	1	100HA	100HA	100HA

Fig. (1): Microhardness of FGMs at different (n) values.

Fig. (2): Microhardness as a function for thickness of implant in FGMs at different n values.

Fig. (3): Compressive strength for FGMs.

Fig. (4): The elastic modulus for FGM at different (n).

Fig. (5): The Poisson's ratio for FGM at different (n).